

Quantum Density $W^*(x)W(x)$ versus Classical Density $\text{constant}/\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$ Part II

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In Part I, we suggested that $W^*(x)W(x) dx = P(x)dx$ for a quantum bound system must become $C/|v(x)| dx = P(x)dx$ for a classical system in the very high energy level limit by arguing that dx behaves as \hbar/p_{ave} , where p_{ave} applies to a very sharp quantum W crest. We argued that if dt is the measure of probability (as it is in the classical case), then for $\exp(-iEt)$ where E is the kinetic energy of a free particle at x (because the particle is essentially localized by very sharp crests), $dt = \hbar/E$ where $E = p_{ave}(x)p_{ave}(x)/2m$. If $dt_{quantum} = W^*(x)W(x) dx$ and dx goes as \hbar/p_{ave} , then $W^*(x)W(x)$ goes as $1/p_{ave}(x)$ or $1/|v(x)|$.

Here we use a somewhat different argument to arrive at the same conclusion. We argue that for all energy levels, $W^*(x)W(x)dx$ is the amount of time a particle spends within dx , even though one uses a time-independent Schrodinger equation. The time-independent Schrodinger equation holds for all energy levels, but one really has the notion of a $v_{rms}(x)$ through $\frac{1}{2}mv_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x) = -\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. In order to obtain a strict sense of time linked to velocity, one wishes to have a linear velocity expression. We propose a scenario which shows that $v(x)_{classical} = v_{rms}(x)_{quantum} = \text{average momentum}$. One may then formally use a $\delta t = \delta x / v(x)$ and link it with an area of $W^*(x)W(x)$ based on the area below a line linking two adjacent peaks.

Classical Density

Classical density may be calculated by assuming that probability is proportional to the amount of time, dt , a particle spends in equally sized dx units. Given $dx = v(x) dt(x)$:

$$P(x)dx = dx C / |v(x)| \text{ where } C \text{ is a normalization constant. } \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Furthermore, } \frac{1}{2}mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \text{ so } |v(x)| = \sqrt{2m(E-V(x))} \quad ((2))$$

Quantum Mechanical Free Particle and Bound Particle

The classical density is clearly formulated from the notion of dt . If one considers a free quantum particle, then it spends equal times in each constant length dx unit. One may ignore the concept of time and state that the particle has the same probability to be in each dx , but this is equivalent to the statement that it spends the same time in each dx . The concept of time does not disappear in quantum mechanics, even for the case of the time-independent Schrodinger equation, because one still has $\exp(ipx)$ where $p = mv$ (nonrelativistically) and $v = dx/dt$.

In the case of a bound particle, $W^*(x)W(x)dx = P(x)dx$. Again, one does not directly need to speak about time, but like in the free particle case, $P(x)dx$ is the amount of time that a particle spends within dx . It does not have a different meaning. This, we argue, is key in trying to establish that $W^*(x)W(x)$ goes as $1/|v(x)|$ for high energy levels.

The Quantum Bound Particle

The time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dW}{dx} / W \right) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3))$$

holds for all energy levels n . It leads to crests and troughs in $W(x)$ even in the very high energy limit because one must still calculate curvature in ((3)).

((3)) shows that one has the notion of $v_{rms}(x)$ through $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dW}{dx} / W \right) = .5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x)$, but one does not really have a sense of a velocity by itself, i.e. in linear form. It is true that $v_{rms}(x) = v(x)$ classical, but $v(x)$ classical stands by itself in the classical world, not in ((3)).

The goal then seems to be to find a standalone expression for velocity from which one obtain dt and link it to probability.

Consider a very high energy level scenario consisting of very narrow, closely packed crests and troughs such that the particle is essentially localized within tiny dx regions with an average kinetic energy in such a region given by the classical $.5m v(x)v(x)$.

We consider dx as the base distance between a peak and its adjacent trough and note that dW/dx equals zero for the initial and final points defining dx . Here dx is not the classical constant length unit, but it is small, i.e. on the same order. Using:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dW}{dx} / W \right) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W - \frac{dW}{dx} / W \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((4))$$

and integrating from a crest top to a trough bottom, the first term formally vanishes and

$$0 = \text{Integral} -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W dx - \frac{1}{2m} \text{Integral} dx \frac{dW}{dx} / W \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((5))$$

The first term on the RHS is formally equal to $.5m v(x) v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity at the center point of dx . This is the classical velocity assumption. It formally holds for a x points and all energy levels quantum mechanically. Here we consider dx to be small enough that one may use $.5m v(x)v(x)$ as representing the entire dx region as is done in classical mechanics. The second integral defines the notion of a linear velocity because $dW/dx/W$ is average p . Thus, a linear velocity exists in this region and is proportional to $v(x)$. One no longer needs to make use of a $v_{rms}(x)$ from Average(vv). This only happens because the energy level is high and the distance between a peak and a trough is very small (i.e. of the order of dx in classical mechanics).

Now, within this dx region one has half of a peak and half of a trough. Taking $W(x)W(x)$, one has two half peaks, but they are very close together. We suggest considering the area below a line from the top of the first peak of $W(x)W(x)$ to the top of the adjacent peak as representing quantum probability $P(x)$. This is an approximation, but we believe it is warranted in the $n \rightarrow$ infinite limit, because the particle is not really excluded from any x as $p \rightarrow$ infinite.

As a result, $\int W(x)W(x) dx$ (area under a curve joining peaks) should equal dt . ((6))

Given that $v(x)$ is defined within dx , then $dt = dx/v(x)$ ((7))

As a result, we argue that in the high energy limit: $\int W(x)W(x) dx \rightarrow 1/|v(x)|$, the classical limit.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of time does not disappear in a quantum bound system and that $P(x)dx = W(x)W(x)dx$ represents both the probability for a particle to be within dx and the average time dt it spends in dx .

The time-independent Schrodinger equation applies for all energy levels and leads to a system of crests and troughs which do not exist in classical physics. Nevertheless, because it is based on conservation of energy, which uses a classical $V(x)$, one has the relationship: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} / W = \frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity. This holds for all energy levels. The problem is that average kinetic energy in quantum mechanics involves $\langle p^2 \rangle$ which is linked to a $v_{rms}(x)$. A linear velocity does not naturally appear and so it is not clear how to obtain dt .

In the high n limit, however, one has very narrow peaks and troughs. We suggest integrating:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dW}{dx} / W \right) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W - \frac{dW}{dx} / W \cdot \frac{dW}{dx} / W$$

over a dx region from the top of the crest to the bottom of a trough so the first term on the LHS vanishes. The second term is proportional to $v(x)v(x)$ because dx is tiny (at the level of a classical dx , but not constant), so $dW/dx/W$ shows the emergence of a linear velocity which is equivalent to $v(x)$. Thus, we argue that the notion of dt appears and is given by $dt = dx/v(x)$ within the quantum dx length. In general, $\int W(x)W(x)dx$ is the area under crests, but we suggest using the approximate area under a line joining a peak of $W(x)W(x)$ to its adjacent peak. As $n \rightarrow$ infinite this approximation should be fine. This area must formally represent the time spend in that region, which in turn is the dt linked with velocity in the same region.

Thus, the area under a curve touching the peaks of $W(x)W(x)$ should become $1/|v(x)|$ in the very high n limit.